

THE ROLE OF CASH ACCOUNTING IN MAINTAINING FINANCIAL DISCIPLINE WITHIN BUDGETARY ORGANIZATIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

IDRISSOVA ANEL BATYRBEK KYZY

Master's student of the «Accounting and Auditing» Educational Program
L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University
Astana, Kazakhstan

AKIMOVA BIBIGUL ZHARMUKHAMETOVNA

Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor of «Accounting and Analysis»
Department
L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University
Astana, Kazakhstan

Annotation: *The purpose of this study is to identify the impact of high-quality cash accounting on the effectiveness of financial discipline in the public sector of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The problem addressed in the article lies in insufficient transparency and control over cash flows, which may adversely affect the financial sustainability of organizations. Within the framework of the research, three key objectives are defined: to analyze the theoretical foundations of cash accounting; to assess the state of financial discipline in budgetary organizations; and to develop recommendations for improving accounting processes. The research methodology incorporates both qualitative and quantitative methods of analysis, allowing for a more comprehensive examination of the subject under study. The object of the research comprises budgetary organizations of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which ensures the practical relevance of the findings. The scientific novelty of the study lies in the systematization of key risks of financial discipline violations associated with cash accounting in budgetary organizations of the Republic of Kazakhstan, as well as in substantiating the role of digitalization as a tool of preventive control.*

Keywords: *financial reporting, Budget Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, accounting, cash, treasury system, digital accounting.*

The Budget Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan establishes the legal framework for treasury execution of the budget and cash servicing, thereby forming a unified mechanism for controlling the movement of budgetary funds and ensuring compliance with financial discipline in budgetary organizations [3]. It defines the legal foundations for the functioning of the Single Treasury Account and regulates the procedures for conducting transactions involving budgetary funds. The Code also sets out the mechanisms of interaction among participants in the budget process in the course of cash receipts and disbursements. These provisions ensure the centralization of public financial resource management. An important aspect of the Budget Code is the regulation of financial control issues within budgetary organizations.

It should be noted that under the current legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the organization of internal financial control and internal public audit is regarded as a mandatory element of the budgetary funds management system and is aimed at enhancing efficiency, transparency, and financial discipline in the use of budgetary resources within public authorities and budgetary organizations. This provision is enshrined in the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan “On State Audit and Financial Control,” as amended and supplemented as of 2025 [4]. It is intended to strengthen accountability for the targeted use of public funds. The implementation of such mechanisms contributes to increased transparency of operations involving budgetary resources.

The Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan “On Accounting and Financial Reporting” establishes unified requirements for the documentary support of cash transactions. It defines the mandatory details of primary accounting documents and the procedures for their preparation when conducting cash operations. The Law prescribes the timely recording of all business transactions in accounting

registers. Compliance with these requirements ensures the reliability of financial information. The specificity of the Law is reflected in the detailed regulation of document flow procedures related to cash transactions. It governs the preparation of cash vouchers, bank statements, and other primary documents. Particular attention is paid to the deadlines for submitting financial statements on transactions involving budgetary funds. These provisions contribute to the unification of accounting processes across all budgetary organizations in the country [5].

Cash operations play a particularly significant role in the system of cash accounting, as this stage is associated with the highest risks of financial discipline violations and misuse of funds. It should be noted that cash transactions in tenge are regulated by regulatory acts establishing maximum limits for cash balances. In the Republic of Kazakhstan, the procedure for conducting cash operations in the national currency (tenge), the rules for the storage and disbursement of cash, as well as the maximum allowable cash balance limits, are governed by regulatory acts of the National Bank of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The key documents include the Rules for Conducting Cash Operations with Individuals and Legal Entities (Resolution of the Board of the National Bank of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated September 28, 2020, No. 120) and the Regulation on Maximum Limits for Cash Withdrawals by Legal Entities from Bank Accounts (Resolution of the Board of the National Bank of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated April 21, 2020, No. 50), which establish the procedures for cash operations and the maximum amounts of cash withdrawals in tenge for legal entities [6, 7]. The cash balance limit is determined individually for each budgetary organization, taking into account the scale of its activities, and is agreed upon with the servicing bank. Any excess over the установленный limit requires the mandatory deposit of surplus cash with a banking institution within the prescribed timeframes. These measures are aimed at minimizing the risks of misuse of funds and ensuring the safeguarding of assets. The procedure for cash collection is regulated by strict requirements for the preparation of accompanying documentation. Each transaction involving the deposit of cash proceeds is accompanied by the issuance of a cash disbursement voucher and a remittance statement for the cash-in-transit bag. Timely transfer of cash to the bank ensures the transparency of cash flows and prevents the accumulation of unrecorded funds. Compliance with cash collection deadlines is monitored by both internal auditors and external audit bodies.

In order to minimize the aforementioned risks and ensure centralized control over the movement of budgetary funds, the principle of treasury single account (cash unity principle) is implemented in the Republic of Kazakhstan. Within budgetary organizations of the Republic of Kazakhstan, this principle implies the centralization of all cash flows through the system of treasury accounts. This approach is enshrined in the Budget Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan and ensures uniformity of accounting procedures [3]. Its implementation makes it possible to consolidate financial resources at the level of the state budget, thereby minimizing the risks of unauthorized use of funds. Centralized recording of transactions forms the basis for effective liquidity management of the budgetary system. The implementation of the treasury single account principle contributes to enhanced transparency of financial operations of budgetary organizations. All receipts and disbursements are recorded in the State Treasury Information System of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which enables real-time monitoring of cash flows. This mechanism eliminates the possibility of opening parallel accounts in commercial banks, thereby strengthening financial discipline. The system of treasury accounts serves as an instrument of both preliminary and ongoing control over the targeted nature of expenditures. The technical implementation of the treasury single account principle is carried out through the integration of accounting systems of budgetary organizations with the state treasury information system. This allows for the automation of cash accounting processes and financial reporting. Each transaction is subject to mandatory registration with the assignment of a unique identifier, ensuring full traceability. Such an accounting architecture is consistent with international standards of public financial management.

Despite the high level of centralization of cash flows, the effectiveness of financial discipline is largely determined by the quality of primary accounting documentation, as it is at this stage that the initial information for accounting and control is formed. Control over the targeted use of budgetary

funds in the Republic of Kazakhstan is exercised through strict regulation of the preparation of primary accounting and cash documents. Requirements for the execution of payment orders, advance reports, and other documents are established by the Budget Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan “On Accounting and Financial Reporting,” as well as subordinate regulatory legal acts of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Kazakhstan governing the authorization and recording of cash transactions [3, 5].

An analysis of the preparation of payment orders and primary cash documents in budgetary organizations conducted by A. Valeev identified more than 500 typical violations and deficiencies, systematized by individual sections with references to the relevant regulatory legal acts [17]. This analysis makes it possible to identify a typology of violations comparable to the practices observed in budgetary organizations of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Similar violations are also revealed in the activities of budgetary organizations in the Republic of Kazakhstan, as evidenced by materials from official reports of state audit bodies, which systematize typical errors in the preparation of primary accounting documents and in compliance with budgetary procedures [13].

The methodology and organization of cash accounting in budgetary organizations of the Republic of Kazakhstan are formed within the framework of the existing regulatory and legal environment, which defines the procedures for conducting cash operations and recording cash flows. Regulation of cash accounting in budgetary organizations is based on a system of legislative acts, the key among which are the Budget Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan “On Accounting and Financial Reporting,” as well as subordinate regulatory legal acts and guidelines of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Kazakhstan. These regulations establish unified requirements for the documentary support of transactions and the procedures for their recording in accounting registers [3, 5].

The comprehensive nature of regulation in the public finance and budgetary sphere is confirmed by the practice of interagency cooperation in the Republic of Kazakhstan. In particular, the Accounts Committee for Control over the Execution of the Republican Budget of the Republic of Kazakhstan, within the scope of its supervisory activities, annually summarizes the results of audits of budgetary organizations. The official analytical reviews of this body “present the main violations and deficiencies identified by control authorities in the public finance and budgetary sphere, systematized by stages of the budget process,” which makes it possible to identify systemic problems and formulate proposals for improving the regulatory framework [8]. Such mechanisms contribute to enhancing the effectiveness of financial control and improving accounting practices in budgetary organizations.

Systemic and recurring violations identified by supervisory authorities indicate the need to shift from predominantly ex post control to preventive mechanisms, the key element of which is the digitalization of accounting and cash operations. As noted by D.A. Batraeva, “digital accounting represents a set of software solutions aimed at automating and optimizing financial processes within organizations” [1]. The implementation of specialized software products makes it possible to minimize manual operations and reduce the risk of errors in payment processing. Settlements through the bank accounts of budgetary organizations are carried out via the treasury system, which ensures centralized control over the movement of funds. The mandatory use of electronic payment systems accelerates the processing of payments and creates an electronic audit trail for subsequent review. Modern data encryption technologies and electronic digital signatures guarantee the security of transactions performed.

An analysis of typical financial discipline violations related to cash accounting shows that deficiencies in the documentary support of transactions are systemic in nature within budgetary organizations of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Violations in the preparation of primary accounting documents for cash flows are manifested in incomplete completion of mandatory details, untimely recording of transactions, and discrepancies between primary documents and accounting registers, which complicate subsequent control over the targeted use of budgetary funds and create risks of distortion of financial reporting.

As noted by G.K. Sagyndykova, among the most common violations observed in the practice of budgetary organizations of the Republic of Kazakhstan are non-compliance with established procedures for the documentary formalization of transactions, the assumption of obligations in excess of approved limits, and insufficient control over cash flows, which indicates weaknesses in the organization of internal financial control [9].

The reasons for the revealed violations in Kazakh practice are, firstly, non-compliance with the requirements for primary documents and forms approved by the authorized body: Accounting rules establish the general procedure for the formation and movement of primary documents, as well as their obligation to reflect transactions in accounting [10]. In addition, there are approved forms of primary accounting documents, non-compliance with which increases the risk of documents being recognized as improperly executed and claims arising during inspections [11]. Secondly, the personnel factor and the quality of professional skills directly affect the completeness of the details and the correctness of the design: professional explanations indicate that incorrectly executed primary documents may entail contesting expenses and other negative consequences, which in practice is most often associated with errors in the design and verification of documents [12]. Thirdly, incomplete automation and insufficient "built-in" data verification in accounting processes increase the risk of missing mandatory details and delays in document processing.; Research on the digitalization of accounting emphasizes that digital solutions reduce the proportion of manual operations, but with incomplete digital maturity of the organization, the likelihood of errors and "gaps" in control remains [1]. As a result, violations lead to delays in reporting and make it difficult to accurately track the movement of budget funds.

A comparative analysis of accounting practices in budgetary organizations of the Republic of Kazakhstan demonstrates a direct relationship between the level of organization of accounting systems and the state of financial discipline. Organizations that have implemented automated cash accounting systems generally exhibit higher accuracy of financial reporting and greater timeliness in recording transactions. In contrast, where manual data processing predominates, arithmetic errors and delays in the recording of cash transactions are more frequently observed. This indicates that the technological capacity of accounting processes is a significant factor in ensuring financial discipline and reducing budgetary risks.

Official results of control activities also indicate the scale and structure of violations in the public finance and budgetary sphere. According to one report of the Supreme Audit Chamber, the audit identified financial violations amounting to KZT 4.1 billion, as well as 203 procedural violations (including those related to budgetary procedures and documentation) [13]. In addition, the practice of internal state audit demonstrates that the quality of accounting and control procedures directly affects the correctness of the classification of violations. According to data from the Committee of Internal State Audit of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Kazakhstan, in the first half of 2022, quality control of audit materials revealed cases in which violations totaling KZT 5,866,648.4 thousand were reclassified as procedural due to insufficient substantiation of auditors' conclusions [14]. Taken together, these findings confirm the need to standardize accounting procedures and strengthen digital control mechanisms as instruments for enhancing financial discipline.

The study confirms an inverse relationship between the quality of internal control over cash flows and the frequency of financial violations: strengthening control procedures enhances the early detection of deviations and reduces the risk of their accumulation. The practice of quality control within internal state audit demonstrates that the quality of control procedures directly affects the accuracy of recording and classifying violations. In the first half of 2022, the Committee of Internal State Audit of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Kazakhstan conducted quality reviews of 288 audit materials, of which 23 were found to be non-compliant with established standards. As a result of quality control reviews, financial violations totaling KZT 7,441,705.5 thousand were recorded, while violations amounting to KZT 5,866,648.4 thousand were reclassified as procedural due to insufficient substantiation of auditors' conclusions [14].

Digitalization of procedures also strengthens the preventive effect of control by accelerating and formalizing document workflows. The scale of the treasury's digital infrastructure is confirmed by data from the Treasury Committee: in 2024, treasury bodies processed 117 million invoices for payment and payment orders, and the number of payment documents increased by 11% compared to 2023 [15]. In addition, the introduction of electronic control formats is закреплено in the rules of electronic internal state audit, which are explicitly aimed at reducing the duration of audit procedures; at the same time, certain audit results are subject to mandatory registration within established timeframes (within three working days after approval of the audit report) [16].

Ways to Optimize Accounting Procedures to Enhance Financial Discipline

The implementation of automated cash flow accounting systems represents a key direction for optimizing accounting processes. Automation minimizes manual effort in processing primary documents and performing settlement operations. This reduces the risk of arithmetic errors and unauthorized data manipulation. Technological solutions enhance the transparency of transactions and shorten the time required to close reporting periods.

The integration of specialized software with accounting platforms significantly enhances the effectiveness of analytical procedures in budgetary organizations. The use of spreadsheets and accounting information systems within a unified information environment makes it possible to automate computational and analytical operations and ensure consistency between analytical indicators and accounting data. As noted in studies by Kazakhstani scholars, the integration of accounting and management information systems contributes to the formation of an integrated database, increases the efficiency of information processing, and expands the capacity for financial control over cash flows [2]. Such integration creates a unified information space for real-time monitoring of cash balances and movements and contributes to greater transparency of accounting and control procedures.

Regular monitoring of cash discipline ensures the timely identification of deviations from established standards and enables the prevention of violations at an early stage. Scheduled inspections of compliance with cash balance limits and deadlines for depositing cash receipts contribute to preventing the misuse of budgetary funds. Operational analysis of cash gaps makes it possible to adjust payment schedules in line with current liquidity conditions. The systematic nature of control procedures creates conditions for preventing violations before they actually occur. The preparation of structured reports on the results of control activities carried out by the accounting department on a regular basis enhances the accountability of responsible personnel and the transparency of accounting processes. Such reports are used as a tool for assessing the effectiveness of existing procedures and serve as a basis for adjusting accounting policies and improving internal regulations of a budgetary organization.

The conducted study has confirmed that the existing regulatory and legal framework for cash accounting in the Republic of Kazakhstan creates the necessary conditions for maintaining financial discipline in budgetary organizations. However, an analysis of legislative acts has revealed the need for their continuous updating in the context of the digital transformation of the budget process and contemporary economic challenges. This necessitates the harmonization of accounting standards with international practice while preserving national specificities in the control of public resources.

The proposed recommendations comprise a set of measures aimed at improving cash accounting in order to minimize violations of financial discipline. The implementation of digital platforms to automate accounting processes will ensure the timeliness and transparency of transaction recording, while the simultaneous transition to a risk-oriented internal control framework will create mechanisms for the early detection of deviations and the prevention of the misuse of funds. An important element of the proposed approach is the systematic enhancement of the qualifications of personnel in the financial departments of budgetary organizations. Specialized training in modern accounting and control methods will strengthen human capital, which, in combination with technological solutions, will form a sustainable system for ensuring financial discipline. The

implementation of these measures will contribute to increased accountability and more effective management of public resources in line with the objectives of budgetary reform.

REFERENCES

1. Batraeva D.A. Transformatsiya bukhgalterskogo ucheta v tsifrovuyu epokhu: vyzovy i perspektivy ekonomicheskoy bezopasnosti [Transformation of accounting in the digital age: challenges and prospects of economic security]. *Biznes i obshchestvo*, 2025, no. 2, pp. 1–5. (In Russian).
2. Nizamdinova A.K. Integratsiya bukhgalterskikh i upravlencheskikh informatsionnykh sistem v Respublike Kazakhstan [Integration of accounting and management information systems in the Republic of Kazakhstan]. *Investment, Finance and Accounting*, 2025, no. 1. Available at: <https://caer.narxoz.kz/jour/article/view/1349> (accessed 20 January 2026).
3. Budget Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 171-VIII dated March 15, 2025 (as amended). Available at: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/K2500000171> (accessed 20 January 2026).
4. Law on State Audit and Financial Control. Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 392-V dated November 12, 2015 (as amended). Available at: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/Z1500000392> (accessed 20 January 2026).
5. Law on Accounting and Financial Reporting. Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 234 dated February 28, 2007 (as amended as of January 1, 2026). Available at: https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/Z070000234_ (accessed 20 January 2026).
6. On approval of the Rules for conducting cash operations with individuals and legal entities. Resolution of the Board of the National Bank of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 120 dated September 28, 2020 (as amended as of December 24, 2025). Available at: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V2000021299> (accessed 20 January 2026).
7. On maximum amounts of cash withdrawals by legal entities from bank accounts during a calendar month. Resolution of the Board of the National Bank of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 50 dated April 21, 2020. Available at: https://online.zakon.kz/Document/?doc_id=39953746 (accessed 20 January 2026).
8. Accounts Committee for Control over Execution of the Republican Budget of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Report on the results of state audit and financial control for 2022. Astana, 2023. Available at: https://www.gov.kz/uploads/2023/5/18/flf30399b1cf29f090a2a7a396645d20_original.452477.pdf (accessed 20 January 2026).
9. Sagyndykova G.K. Problemy finansovogo kontrolya i bukhgalterskogo ucheta v byudzhetykh organizatsiyakh Respubliki Kazakhstan [Problems of financial control and accounting in budgetary organizations of the Republic of Kazakhstan]. *Finansy Kazakhstana*, 2021, no. 6, pp. 52–58. (In Russian).
10. On approval of the Rules for accounting. Order of the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 241 dated March 31, 2015 (registered with the Ministry of Justice on May 6, 2015 No. 10954). Available at: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V1500010954> (accessed 20 January 2026).
11. On approval of the forms of primary accounting documents. Order of the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 562 dated December 20, 2012. Available at: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V1200008265> (accessed 20 January 2026).
12. Kim L. Kakie riski voznikayut pri prinyatii k uchetu nekorrektno oformlennykh pervichnykh dokumentov? [What risks arise when incorrectly executed primary documents are recognized in accounting?]. Paragraph Information System, August 20, 2015. Available at: https://prg.kz/Document/?doc_id=34351822 (accessed 20 January 2026).

13. The Supreme Audit Chamber identified financial violations totaling 4.1 billion tenge and 203 procedural violations following the audit in Ulytau region. May 22, 2024. Available at: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/esep/press/news/details/775802?lang=ru> (accessed 20 January 2026).
14. Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Committee of Internal State Audit. Results of second-level quality control for the first half of 2022. Astana, 2022. Available at: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/minfin/press/news/details/404351?lang=ru> (accessed 20 January 2026).
15. Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Treasury Committee. Key performance results of the Treasury Committee for 2024. Astana, 2024. Available at: https://www.gov.kz/uploads/2025/5/14/29a414f24413cf7980feec609c1b1b5_original.1751315.pdf (accessed 20 January 2026).
16. Procedure for electronic internal public audit approved in Kazakhstan. Kazinform, January 13, 2026. Available at: <https://www.inform.kz/ru/poryadok-elektronnogo-vnutrennego-gosaudita-utverdili-v-kazahstane-decb76> (accessed 20 January 2026).
17. Valeev A. Analiz narusheniy pri oformlenii pervichnykh uchetykh i platezhnykh dokumentov v byudzhetnykh organizatsiyakh [Analysis of violations in the preparation of primary accounting and payment documents in budgetary organizations]. *Finansovyy kontrol*, 2016, no. 4, pp. 45–52. (In Russian).